

Insect management

Pest abundance in sequentially planted crops

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We studied the impact of time of crop establishment on relative abundance of pests in Sierra Bullones, Bohol, Philippines Aug 1987-Jan 1988. Three neighboring 0.6-ha fields were planted at monthly intervals with tungro (RTV)-susceptible IR64, first planting in Aug (normal planting), the second in Sep, the third in Oct.

Green leafhopper (GLH) populations were monitored by weekly sweep net

sampling from seedling stage to about 60 days after transplanting (DT). The pest population showed a gradual but steady increase, with a peak during maximum tillering. A significantly higher GLH population density was recorded on the third planting (see table). Peak catches of GLH in the kerosene light trap indicated a gradual increase in GLH activity in the area (see figure).

Although RTV infection in general

was too low to cause significant yield loss, RTV incidence tended to increase from the first planting to the third.

Because of negligible pest incidence, yield from the first planting was significantly higher than that from the second and third plantings. High thrips incidence during the vegetative stage of the second planting and high incidence of caseworm and rice bug coupled with severe damage by rats in the third planting contributed to lower yields. □

Pest incidence and yield on sequentially planted IR64 crops.^a Sierra Bullones, Bohol, Philippines, 1987-88.

Cropping period	Rat damage	GLH (mean/3 wk, 10 sweeps each)	Rice bugs (no./m ²)	Caseworm (larvae/m ²)	Thrips (no./leaf)	Yield (t/ha + SEM)
Aug-Nov 1987	Negligible	14 a	0	0	0	6.1 + 0.31 a
Sep-Dec 1987	Negligible	13 a	0	0	9	5.4 + 0.25 b
Oct 1987-Jan 1988	Severe	26 b	18	11	0	2.6 + 0.08 c

^aIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Seasonal population density of GLH monitored by sweep net and kerosene light trap (KLT). Hopper numbers are based on (A) weekly catches in 10 sweeps made on sequentially planted crops of IR64 and on (B) daily catches in KLT. Sierra Bullones, Bohol, Philippines, 1987.